

Awareness and Use of Turnitin software by Academic Staff in Ensuring Academic Integrity in Nigerian Universities

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Abstract

This study examines the awareness and use of Turnitin among academic staff in ensuring academic integrity in universities in South-Western Nigeria. The study was motivated by the growing concern over plagiarism and academic misconduct in higher education, particularly in the context of increased access to digital information resources. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, and data were collected from 132 academic staff across five universities: Lagos State University, University of Ibadan, Ogun State University (Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ekiti State University, and Osun State University). The findings reveal that although awareness of Turnitin is relatively high, its consistent use among academic staff remains low. Most respondents utilize the software primarily at the final stages of research evaluation rather than as a continuous instructional tool. The study also shows that while Turnitin is widely perceived as effective in detecting plagiarism and improving students' academic writing, its role in promoting academic integrity and discouraging plagiarism is considered limited. Key challenges identified include misleading similarity reports, insufficient institutional support, technical difficulties, and poor internet connectivity. Furthermore, respondents emphasized the need for improved integration of Turnitin with learning management systems, stronger institutional policies, enhanced internet infrastructure, and continuous training for both staff and students. The study concludes

Received: 14 May 2026

Revised: 15 May 2026

Accepted: 18 May 2026

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26643/ijr/61>

that while Turnitin is a valuable tool for supporting academic integrity, its effectiveness depends largely on proper usage, user competence, and institutional support. The study recommends a holistic approach combining technology, policy enforcement, and capacity building to enhance its impact in Nigerian universities.

Keywords: Turnitin; Academic Integrity; Plagiarism Detection; Nigerian Universities; Academic Staff; Technology Adoption

Introduction

Academic integrity has emerged as a fundamental core value of higher education systems globally, especially in an era defined by the rapid advancement of digital technologies and unprecedented access to online information resources. The transformation of the academic landscape through the internet, digital libraries, open-access repositories, and artificial intelligence tools has significantly reshaped how knowledge is created, stored, disseminated, and used. While these technological developments have enhanced learning opportunities and facilitated research productivity, they have simultaneously introduced complex challenges related to the ethical use of information.

In today's academic environment, students and researchers are no longer limited to physical libraries; instead, they operate within a cavernous digital landscape where information is readily available at the click of a button. While this convenience enhances access to information and knowledge, it also changes the line between originally conducted research work and the reuse of existing ideas and concepts, increasing the risk of academic misconduct, particularly plagiarism. As a result, institutions now face growing challenges in monitoring, maintaining and upholding standards of originality and proper citation, given how easily digital content can be copied, modified, or reused without acknowledgment.

According to Olujuwon and Ojo (2024), plagiarism is the exploitation of another person's intellectual work without giving due credit, which damages academic institutions' reputations and lowers the calibre of research products. The problem is especially severe in developing nations like Nigeria because of structural issues like poor research training, lax enforcement of academic rules, and a lack of knowledge about moral scholarly conduct.

The situation is made worse by students' and faculty members' differing degrees of digital literacy. While some are adept at using digital resources ethically, others are not well-versed in scholarly writing styles, citation techniques, and paraphrasing. As a result, incidents of plagiarism might not necessarily be deliberate but instead result from

a lack of knowledge of the fundamentals of academic integrity. However, such actions compromise the integrity of intellectual work and the validity of academic credentials, whether intentional or unintentional.

In response to the growing threat of academic dishonesty, educational institutions, especially universities are increasingly adopting technological tools such as Turnitin, a web-based plagiarism detection software designed to promote originality and uphold academic standards. Turnitin software works by comparing submitted texts against a wide range of sources, including academic publications, internet content, and previously submitted papers. This process allows educators to detect similarities in text and identify potential cases of plagiarism. The integration of such technologies into higher education reflects a broader shift toward the use of artificial intelligence and digital systems in safeguarding academic integrity (Njoku et al., 2025).

Regulatory bodies in Nigeria, particularly the National Universities Commission, have advocated for the integration of plagiarism detection tools such as Turnitin into university systems as part of broader quality assurance practices in teaching and research (Abduldayan, Yusuf, and Olatunde 2019). The author added that this policy direction reflects a clear recognition of plagiarism as a significant threat to both the credibility of academic qualifications and the reputation of institutions.

Existing research indicates that the effectiveness of these tools largely depends on how well academic staff and students understand, accept, and use them appropriately. However, the level of awareness, accessibility, and effective use of Turnitin software among academic staff may vary significantly. While some lecturers may lack adequate training or institutional support, others may not fully integrate the software into their teaching and assessment practices. It is against this backdrop that this study is being conducted.

Research Objectives

The general objective of this study is to examine the awareness and use of Turnitin software by academic staff in ensuring academic integrity in universities in South-Western Nigeria.

Specific Objectives

1. To determine the level of awareness of Turnitin software among academic staff.
2. To assess the extent of use of Turnitin software in teaching and assessment.
3. To evaluate academic staff perceptions of the effectiveness of Turnitin in ensuring academic integrity.
4. To identify the challenges faced by academic staff in using Turnitin software.
5. To suggest strategies for improving the use of Turnitin in promoting academic integrity.

Received: 14 May 2026

Revised: 15 May 2026

Accepted: 18 May 2026

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26643/ijr/61>

Research Questions

1. What is the level of awareness of Turnitin software among academic staff in universities in South-Western Nigeria?
2. To what extent do academic staff use Turnitin software in their teaching and assessment practices?
3. What are the perceptions of academic staff regarding the effectiveness of Turnitin in ensuring academic integrity?
4. What challenges do academic staff face in the use of Turnitin software?
5. What strategies can enhance the effective use of Turnitin in promoting academic integrity?

Literature Review: Conceptual, Theoretical and Empirical

Academic integrity is a fundamental principle in higher education that emphasizes honesty, trust, fairness, and responsibility in teaching, learning, and research processes (International Center for Academic Integrity, 2021). It ensures that scholarly work is original and properly acknowledges sources, thereby preserving the credibility of academic qualifications (International Center for Academic Integrity, 2021). However, the increasing availability of digital resources has contributed to rising cases of plagiarism in universities, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria, where weak enforcement mechanisms and inadequate awareness persist (Bretag, 2013). Awareness and users' perceptions of these technologies are key factors influencing their adoption and effective use (Kashada, Li, and Koshadah, 2018).

Plagiarism, defined as the presentation of another person's ideas or work without proper attribution, remains one of the most prevalent forms of academic misconduct (Purdue Online Writing Lab, 2020).

The introduction of plagiarism detection tools such as Turnitin, which analyze submitted work against extensive databases to identify similarities and promote academic integrity, has been widely adopted as a solution to plagiarism (Vrbanec & Merovic, 2020). However, their effectiveness is often limited because many educators have only a basic understanding of how the system works and struggle to properly interpret similarity reports. According to Garba (2018), the consistent use of such software in academic evaluation is further hindered by inadequate training and insufficient institutional support. To combat plagiarism and enhance students' academic writing skills, many universities have adopted plagiarism detection tools like Turnitin (Kokkinaki, Demoliou, and Iakovidou, 2015) as a means of reducing instances of academic dishonesty.

Vrbanec & Meštrovic (2020), the emergence of plagiarism detection technologies such as Turnitin has been widely adopted to address this challenge by comparing submitted

texts with extensive databases to identify similarities and promote originality in academic writing.

Studies have shown that many academics possess only moderate awareness of Turnitin and limited knowledge of how to interpret similarity reports, which reduces its effectiveness in combating plagiarism (Garba, 2018). The author further stated that inadequate training and lack of institutional support often hinder the consistent use of the software in academic assessment.

Jereb et al. (2018) investigated the factors contributing to plagiarism among students in Germany and Slovenia, identifying the rise of new technologies and widespread internet use as major influences. Similarly, Kayaoglu et al. (2015) explored cross-cultural perceptions of plagiarism among Turkish, German, and Georgian students. Although notable differences existed among the groups, common causes of plagiarism included misuse of online resources, inadequate citation practices, weak academic writing skills, and poor time management.

This study is grounded in three major theoretical frameworks, each contributing distinct perspectives. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Fred Davis in 1986 and later validated in 1989, explains how users come to accept and use technology. The model emphasizes that adoption is primarily influenced by two factors: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use.

Deterrence Theory, rooted in classical criminology, was first articulated by Cesare Beccaria in 1764 in *On Crimes and Punishments*. He argued that crime can be minimized when punishment is certain, swift, and proportionate. This idea was further expanded by Jeremy Bentham, who introduced the utilitarian perspective, suggesting that individuals act rationally by weighing potential benefits against possible consequences before engaging in misconduct.

Protection Motivation Theory (PMT), proposed by R. W. Rogers in 1975 and later revised in 1983, explains how individuals respond to perceived threats. The theory highlights two key processes: threat appraisal and coping appraisal. It suggests that protective behavior is influenced by perceived severity, vulnerability, response efficacy, and self-efficacy.

Collectively, these frameworks provide a comprehensive basis for understanding technology adoption, behavioral regulation, and responses to risk. They are particularly relevant in examining the awareness and use of plagiarism detection tools such as Turnitin in academic environments.

TAM suggests that academic staff are more likely to adopt Turnitin when they perceive it as useful for detecting plagiarism and easy to use. This underscores the need for

institutions to provide not only access to such tools but also adequate training and support to enhance user competence.

Deterrence Theory complements this by explaining that the likelihood of academic misconduct decreases when individuals perceive a high probability of detection and punishment. Turnitin serves as a deterrent by increasing the chances of identifying plagiarized work, thereby discouraging dishonest practices and reinforcing a culture of academic integrity.

Similarly, PMT explains that individuals are more inclined to adopt preventive measures when they recognize the seriousness of a threat and believe in their ability to address it. In this context, both students and staff may use Turnitin to avoid the consequences of plagiarism, driven by their awareness of risks and confidence in the tool's effectiveness.

Empirical evidence supports the application of these theories. A study conducted at the University of Ibadan found that while Turnitin is widely regarded as a valuable tool for promoting academic integrity, its effectiveness is limited by technical challenges and the lack of standardized institutional policies. This highlights the combined influence of technological, behavioral, and institutional factors on its successful use.

Furthermore, the integration of TAM, Deterrence Theory, and PMT offers a holistic understanding of the factors influencing the adoption and use of Turnitin. While TAM focuses on user acceptance, Deterrence Theory emphasizes enforcement, and PMT explains responses to perceived threats. Together, they demonstrate that the effective implementation of plagiarism detection tools depends on accessibility, user training, and strong institutional support systems.

Empirical studies have explored the level of awareness and utilization of Turnitin in higher education institutions. In Nigeria, a study conducted at Bayero University Kano found that although academic staff possessed a moderate level of awareness of Turnitin, its actual use for plagiarism detection remained low, highlighting a disconnect between knowledge and practical application (Garba, 2018).

Similarly, research at the Federal University of Technology, Minna showed that despite the introduction of Turnitin to address plagiarism, both students and staff exhibited limited understanding of plagiarism and minimal engagement with the software, which reduced its overall effectiveness (Abduldayan et al., 2019).

Beyond Nigeria, studies across other African institutions indicate that while Turnitin is widely adopted to enhance academic writing and detect plagiarism, several challenges persist. These include insufficient training, misinterpretation of similarity reports, and overdependence on the software (Nketsiah et al., 2023). Furthermore, recent findings highlight certain limitations of Turnitin, such as false positives and difficulty in

Received: 14 May 2026

Revised: 15 May 2026

Accepted: 18 May 2026

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detecting paraphrased or non-English content, which may affect its reliability in maintaining academic integrity (Ilori, 2025).

Generally, the literature suggests that although Turnitin plays an important role in promoting academic integrity in Nigerian universities, its effectiveness depends largely on users' awareness, proper training, and consistent application. The observed gap between awareness and actual use, along with institutional and technical constraints, emphasizes the need for continuous capacity building, stronger policy enforcement, and better integration of Turnitin into teaching and research practices.

Methodology

This study adopts a descriptive survey research design to investigate the awareness and use of Turnitin among academic staff in ensuring academic integrity in universities in South-Western Nigeria. The population of the study consists of 132 academic staff drawn from selected federal and state-owned universities in the region, namely Lagos State University, Ekiti State University, University of Ibadan, and Ogun State University (Olabisi Onabanjo University and University of Osun State). A purposive sampling technique was employed to select academic lecturers across faculties in each of the identified institutions, ensuring that respondents have adequate exposure to teaching, assessment practices, and academic writing processes.

Data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire designed to elicit information on respondents' level of awareness, extent of use, perceptions of effectiveness, challenges encountered, and strategies for improving the use of Turnitin software. The questionnaire comprises closed-ended items measured on a Likert scale. The instrument was validated through expert review, and its reliability was established using a pilot test with a small group of academic staff outside the sampled universities, yielding a satisfactory reliability coefficient.

For data analysis, responses were coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages were used to answer the research questions.. The findings are presented in charts for clarity. Ethical considerations, including voluntary participation, confidentiality, and anonymity of respondents were strictly observed throughout the study.

Presentation of Results

Fig.1

Received: 14 May 2026

Revised: 15 May 2026

Accepted: 18 May 2026

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The distribution of respondents across the selected universities shows a fairly balanced representation, with slight variations in participation levels. Lagos State University (LASU) contributed 24 respondents, accounting for 18.2% of the total sample. University of Ibadan (UI) had a slightly higher representation with 29 respondents (22.0%), while Osun State University (OSU) recorded the highest participation at 30 respondents, representing 22.7% of the sample. Ekiti State University (EKSU) contributed 26 respondents (19.7%), and Osun State University (UNIOSUN) had the lowest proportion with 23 respondents, accounting for 17.4% of the total. Overall, the sample size of 132 respondents is relatively evenly distributed across the five institutions, with each university contributing between approximately 17% and 23% of the total responses. This near-uniform distribution enhances the representativeness of the data, reducing the likelihood of institutional bias and allowing for more balanced comparative analysis across the universities. Although OSU has the highest proportion and UNIOSUN the lowest, the differences are marginal, suggesting that no single institution disproportionately influences the overall findings of the study.

Fig. 2

The table indicates that the respondents in the study are predominantly highly educated, with the majority holding advanced degrees. Specifically, 68 respondents, representing 51.5% of the sample, possess a PhD, making it the most common qualification. This is followed by 55 respondents (41.7%) who hold a Master’s degree. In contrast, only 9 respondents, accounting for 6.8%, have a first degree as their highest qualification. Overall, the distribution suggests that the sample is heavily skewed toward individuals with postgraduate education, implying a strong presence of advanced academic expertise among the respondents.

Fig. 3

The table presents the distribution of respondents by academic rank, showing a diverse representation across different levels of the academic hierarchy. The largest proportion of participants were Lecturer I, accounting for 22.7% (30 respondents), indicating that mid-level academics formed the core of the sample. This is followed by Associate Professors/Readers at 20.5% (27 respondents) and Senior Lecturers at 17.4% (23 respondents), further emphasizing a strong presence of experienced academics. Lecturer II made up 13.6% (18 respondents), while Full Professors constituted 11.4% (15 respondents), reflecting a moderate inclusion of senior-most academics. At the lower end, Research Fellows accounted for 7.6% (10 respondents), and Graduate/Assistant Lecturers represented the smallest group at 6.8% (9 respondents). Overall, the distribution suggests that the study captured a balanced mix of academic staff, with a slight concentration in the mid-career ranks, which may provide a well-rounded perspective on the issues investigated.

Received: 14 May 2026

Revised: 15 May 2026

Accepted: 18 May 2026

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Fig. 4

The table presents the distribution of respondents' usage of Turnitin among 132 participants, showing varying levels of engagement with its features. A small proportion of respondents, 7 (5.3%), indicated that they consistently utilize Turnitin to evaluate students' research outcomes, suggesting limited routine use. Meanwhile, 26 respondents (19.7%) reported incorporating Turnitin as part of their instructional

Received: 14 May 2026

Revised: 15 May 2026

Accepted: 18 May 2026

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practices, reflecting a moderate level of integration into teaching activities. In addition, 20 respondents (15.2%) stated that they mandate students to submit their research for Turnitin checks, indicating some enforcement of its use within academic processes.

The highest proportion of respondents, 36 (27.3%), rely on Turnitin reports when making final approval decisions on research work, showing that the software is most commonly used as a final evaluative tool. Closely following this, 34 respondents (25.8%) reported using Turnitin's feedback features, such as comments and grading tools, demonstrating significant engagement with its formative assessment capabilities. Furthermore, 9 respondents (6.8%) encourage students to review their similarity reports before final submission, indicating a smaller but notable emphasis on student self-review and improvement. Overall, the findings reveal that while consistent use of Turnitin remains relatively low, most respondents utilize it at critical stages of the academic process, particularly for final approval and feedback purposes, highlighting its importance as both an evaluative and instructional support tool.

Fig. 4

The table presents respondents' perceptions of the effectiveness of Turnitin based on 132 valid responses. The findings show that 28 respondents (21.2%) believe that Turnitin effectively detects instances of plagiarism in students' work, indicating a generally positive perception of its core function. However, only 7 respondents (5.3%) agreed that Turnitin helps promote academic integrity among students, while 10 respondents (7.6%) felt that its use discourages students from engaging in plagiarism, suggesting relatively low agreement on the impact of Turnitin software.

In terms of reliability and academic support, 24 respondents (18.2%) stated that Turnitin similarity reports are reliable, reflecting moderate confidence in its output. A larger proportion, 36 respondents (27.3%), agreed that Turnitin contributes to enhancing the quality of students' academic writing, making this the most frequently reported perception and highlighting its perceived role in improving writing skills. Furthermore, 27 respondents (20.5%) indicated that Turnitin is a valuable tool for teaching and assessment overall, showing a generally favorable view of its usefulness in academic settings. Overall, the results suggest that while respondents strongly acknowledge Turnitin's role in improving academic writing and detecting plagiarism, its perceived impact on promoting academic integrity and discouraging plagiarism is comparatively weaker. This implies that Turnitin is viewed more as an evaluative and developmental tool rather than a direct behavioral deterrent against academic dishonesty.

Fig. 5

The table presents respondents’ perceptions of the challenges encountered in using Turnitin software. The most frequently reported challenge is that Turnitin sometimes produces similarity reports that can be misleading, with 37 respondents representing 28.0% of the total responses. This suggests that nearly one-third of the users question the accuracy or interpretation of the similarity reports generated by the system.

The second most common challenge is insufficient institutional support for using Turnitin, reported by 28 respondents (21.2%). This indicates that many users may not be receiving adequate administrative or technical backing to effectively utilize the software. Technical difficulties also remain a notable concern, with 24 respondents (18.2%) indicating they experience such issues when using Turnitin.

In addition, 19 respondents (14.4%) reported that poor internet connectivity restricts their efficient use of the platform, highlighting infrastructural limitations that affect access and functionality. Smaller proportions of respondents identified a lack of

adequate training and limited time as challenges, each accounting for 12 respondents (9.1%) respectively. These findings suggest that while technical and institutional issues are more prominent, user preparedness and time constraints also contribute to the challenges experienced. The results imply that effective use of Turnitin software is influenced by a combination of system-related issues, institutional factors, and user capacity constraints, with misleading similarity reports and inadequate support being the most significant concerns.

Fig. 6

The above table presents respondents' views on strategies for enhancing the effective use of Turnitin software. The most strongly supported strategy is the integration of Turnitin with learning management systems, which was selected by 37 respondents, representing 28.0% of the total. This indicates that many users believe seamless integration with existing academic platforms would significantly improve accessibility and usage efficiency.

The next most frequently suggested strategy is the implementation of institutional policies mandating the use of Turnitin, with 27 respondents (20.5%) supporting this option. This suggests that formal enforcement within institutions could play an

important role in ensuring consistent use of the software. Improving internet infrastructure was also highlighted by 22 respondents, accounting for 16.7%, showing that reliable connectivity is seen as essential for effective utilization.

Furthermore, 18 respondents (13.6%) indicated that continuous training would enhance their proficiency in using Turnitin, emphasizing the importance of ongoing capacity building. Both the provision of easily accessible technical support and proper student training were selected by 14 respondents each, representing 10.6% respectively. These findings suggest that while system-level improvements are highly prioritized, user support and skill development remain important complementary strategies.

Overall, the cumulative percentages show a balanced distribution of responses across the proposed strategies, totaling 100%. The results imply that enhancing Turnitin usage requires a combination of technological integration, institutional enforcement, infrastructure improvement, and user-focused training and support systems.

Fig. 7

The table presents respondents' general attitudes toward academic integrity and the use of Turnitin software. The most widely held view is that plagiarism is widespread among

students, with 33 respondents representing 25.0% of the total. This indicates a strong perception that academic dishonesty remains a significant concern in higher education. Closely following this, 29 respondents (22.0%) agreed that academic integrity is a critical issue in higher education, further reinforcing the importance attached to maintaining ethical standards in academic work.

In addition, 26 respondents, accounting for 19.7%, indicated that digital tools like Turnitin are essential in modern education, suggesting a substantial recognition of the role of technology in promoting academic honesty. Meanwhile, 19 respondents (14.4%) expressed confidence in their ability to use Turnitin effectively, showing a moderate level of self-assurance among users.

A smaller proportion of respondents, 14 (10.6%), stated that they are willing to adopt new features of Turnitin, indicating some openness to technological advancement, though not overwhelmingly strong. The least selected response was that their institution encourages ethical academic practices, with 11 respondents (8.3%), which may point to perceived gaps in institutional support or promotion of academic integrity.

Overall, the cumulative percentage reaches 100%, reflecting all responses captured in the table. The findings suggest that while there is strong awareness of the importance of academic integrity and the prevalence of plagiarism, there is comparatively lower confidence in institutional support and moderate readiness among users to fully engage with and adopt Turnitin's capabilities.

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study are largely consistent with existing literature on the adoption and use of Turnitin in higher education. The relatively low proportion of respondents who consistently use Turnitin for evaluating students' research aligns with the findings of Garba (2018), who reported a gap between awareness and actual utilization of the software among academic staff in Nigerian universities. Although respondents in this study demonstrated moderate engagement by incorporating Turnitin into instructional practices and mandating its use in some cases, its predominant use at the final approval stage suggests that it is treated more as a summative evaluation tool than a continuous instructional resource. This pattern reflects the assumptions of the Technology Acceptance Model developed by Fred Davis (1986; 1989), which posits that technology adoption is influenced by perceived usefulness and ease of use. While respondents recognize Turnitin's usefulness in decision-making and feedback, limited routine use may indicate challenges related to usability, training, or institutional support.

In terms of perceived effectiveness, the findings support earlier studies that emphasised Turnitin's strength in detecting plagiarism and improving academic writing. For instance, Kokkinaki et al. (2015) highlighted the role of plagiarism detection tools in enhancing students' writing quality, which corresponds with the high proportion of

Received: 14 May 2026

Revised: 15 May 2026

Accepted: 18 May 2026

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respondents in this study who acknowledged this benefit. Similarly, Vrbanec and Meštrovic (2020) noted that Turnitin is widely used to identify textual similarities and support originality in academic work. However, the relatively low percentage of respondents who believe that Turnitin promotes academic integrity or discourages plagiarism suggests that its impact on behavior is limited. This finding aligns with Tracey Bretag (2013), who argued that technological tools alone are insufficient to enforce ethical academic practices without strong institutional frameworks.

The findings can further be explained using Deterrence Theory as proposed by Cesare Beccaria (1764) and expanded by Jeremy Bentham, which suggests that individuals are less likely to engage in misconduct when there is certainty of detection and punishment. Although Turnitin increases the likelihood of detecting plagiarism, the low perception of its deterrent effect in this study indicates that detection must be complemented by clear institutional policies and enforcement. Likewise, Protection Motivation Theory developed by R. W. Rogers (1975; 1983) helps explain why Turnitin may not significantly influence behavior, as users must perceive both the severity of plagiarism consequences and their ability to avoid them. The findings suggest that such perceptions may not be sufficiently strong among respondents.

The challenges identified in this study, particularly misleading similarity reports, inadequate institutional support, and technical difficulties are strongly supported by previous empirical research. Abduldayan et al. (2019) reported that limited understanding of plagiarism and poor engagement with Turnitin reduce its effectiveness, while Nketsiah et al. (2023) identified insufficient training and misinterpretation of similarity reports as major barriers. Furthermore, Ilori (2025) highlighted issues such as false positives and difficulties in interpreting similarity indices, which corroborates respondents' concerns about misleading reports. Infrastructure-related challenges, such as poor internet connectivity, also align with the observations of United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2017), which emphasized the impact of technological limitations on digital tool adoption in developing countries.

The strategies suggested by respondents for improving Turnitin usage are also consistent with the literature. The strong support for integrating Turnitin with learning management systems reflects the importance of ease of use emphasized in the Technology Acceptance Model (Fred Davis, 1989). Similarly, the call for institutional policies mandating its use aligns with Deterrence Theory (Cesare Beccaria, 1764), which stresses the role of enforcement in shaping behavior. The emphasis on continuous training and technical support further supports the findings of Garba (2018), who noted that inadequate training significantly hinders effective utilization. These results indicate that improving Turnitin adoption requires a combination of technological, institutional, and human capacity interventions.

Finally, the respondents' attitudes toward academic integrity particularly the perception that plagiarism is widespread are consistent with global concerns highlighted in the literature. International Center for Academic Integrity (2021) emphasized the importance of maintaining honesty and responsibility in academic work, while studies such as Jereb et al. (2018) and Kayaoğlu et al. (2015) identified factors such as misuse of digital resources and weak academic writing skills as key drivers of plagiarism. The low confidence in institutional support observed in this study further reinforces the argument by Tracey Bretag (2013) that weak enforcement mechanisms undermine efforts to promote ethical academic practices. Overall, the findings confirm that while Turnitin is a valuable tool for detecting plagiarism and enhancing writing quality, its effectiveness depends on consistent application, proper training, and strong institutional support systems.

Conclusion

The study demonstrates that while Turnitin plays a significant role in detecting plagiarism and enhancing academic writing, its full potential in promoting academic integrity has not yet been realized. Addressing the identified challenges through improved policies, training, infrastructure, and institutional support will significantly enhance its effectiveness in Nigerian universities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Strengthen Institutional Policies**
Universities should establish and enforce clear policies mandating the use of Turnitin in teaching, assessment, and research processes to ensure consistency and accountability.
2. **Provide Continuous Training**
Regular workshops and training programs should be organized for academic staff and students to improve their understanding of Turnitin, particularly in interpreting similarity reports and applying feedback effectively.
3. **Enhance Technical and Institutional Support**
Institutions should provide accessible technical support systems and dedicated personnel to assist users in resolving issues related to Turnitin usage.
4. **Improve Internet Infrastructure**
Reliable internet connectivity should be prioritized to ensure seamless access and efficient use of Turnitin and other digital academic tools.
5. **Integrate Turnitin with Learning Management Systems**
Universities should integrate Turnitin into their existing digital learning platforms to enhance ease of use and encourage its incorporation into routine teaching practices.

6. Promote Academic Integrity Culture
Institutions should actively promote awareness of academic integrity through seminars, campaigns, and inclusion in curricula, ensuring that both staff and students understand its importance.
7. Encourage Formative Use of Turnitin
Academic staff should encourage students to review similarity reports before final submission to promote self-assessment, learning, and improvement in academic writing.

Declarations

Ethics approval: Ethical review was not considered necessary in alignment with the Crawford University's guidance on the conduct of ethical research.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Funding: Not applicable

AI-generated content: No AI tools were used.

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